

OpenFOAM-based decay solver for multi-physics reactor operation, control and safety analysis applications

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ABSTRACT

This work presents the development and first applications of decayFoam, a new solver for an accurate treatment of decay power and poisoning effects, such as Xenon oscillations, for OpenFOAM-based multi-physics applications such as GeN-Foam. The proposed solver implements the Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM) to solve the Bateman equations efficiently and with high stability, avoiding the numerical issues of conventional matrix exponentiation. It is designed for parallel, cell-wise computations, making it suitable for high-resolution and distributed simulations. Verification against the Monte Carlo code Serpent demonstrates excellent agreement, with deviations in decay power below 0.4 % and nuclide concentrations within 0.03 % for selected isotopes. The solver is further coupled with foamForNuclear neutronics and thermal-hydraulics sub-solvers in GeN-Foam to simulate Xenon axial oscillations in a simplified PWR fuel assembly. The results show the expected oscillation period of about 30 hours and illustrate the stabilizing role of Doppler feedback, with oscillations dampening after ≈ 200 hours when temperature effects are included. Although not intended to replace high-fidelity Monte Carlo approaches, decayFoam provides a fast and flexible solution for multi-physics safety scenarios involving decay heat and reactor poisoning.

Keywords: Multi-physics, OpenFOAM, GeN-Foam, decay, Xenon oscillations

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate modeling of nuclear reactor decay power and neutronics poisoning processes is essential for a wide range of nuclear reactor applications, from transient safety analysis and Xenon oscillation prediction to decay heat removal. The Bateman equations follow the evolution of isotopic concentrations under neutron irradiation, releasing heat, radiation, and daughter nuclides. These phenomena are essential not only for predicting reactor behavior during operation, but also for post-shutdown conditions. In particular, residual decay heat is a key parameter for safety and emergency cooling design.

OpenFOAM [1], widely adopted for thermal-hydraulic and multi-physics simulations, has been extended to include neutronics and thermo-mechanics capabilities through the GeN-Foam multi-physics application [2, 3]. However, it currently lacks built-in functionality to evaluate cell-wise decay power after shutdown or the poisoning effects on the reactor core. The only feature available is to provide the total decay power using a timetable, which is not adapted for localized effects studies. Therefore, users must rely on external tools such as the Monte Carlo codes Serpent [4] or OpenMC [5] to evaluate decay power or the reactivity worth of poisons, or generate multi-group cross sections (MGXS).

An alternative approach involves coupling OpenFOAM with Serpent through the built-in Serpent multi-physics interface [6]. Although this enables detailed decay modeling, it often comes at a high computational cost, particularly for large-scale or transient simulations. FISPACT [7], widely used for inventory

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analysis, also provides decay calculations capabilities; however, its integration within a dynamic CFD environment or fully coupled reactor simulation remains limited and typically requires additional interfacing infrastructure.

To address this gap, a dedicated OpenFOAM-based solver, called decayFoam, has been developed for use in the foamForNuclear (FFN) project within the restructured version of GeN-Foam [8]. GeN-Foam has evolved into the application responsible for coupling all FFN libraries and modules in a flexible and general way. decayFoam solves the Bateman equations using a cell-wise formulation, where, at each mesh cell, the full nuclide vector and the corresponding power evolution are computed. Thanks to its object-oriented structure and the foamForNuclear platform, it can be coupled with any physics module of foamForNuclear in the GeN-Foam application for extended multi-physics simulations involving decay and poisoning build-up phenomena. The solver is verified against Serpent with a simplified core case where the nuclide and decay power evolution are computed during cooldown. The solver is then coupled with neutronics and thermal-hydraulics to study Xenon oscillation in a simplified Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) fuel assembly. The solver is not intended for burnup calculations, as explained in the limitation section.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Decay algorithm with external neutron source

The time evolution of nuclide concentrations in a neutron-irradiated system is governed by the Bateman equation, which tracks the production and decay of N nuclear species under the influence of both decay and neutron-induced reactions. In vector form, the governing equation is written as:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{N}}{dt} = \mathbf{M}(\phi)\mathbf{N} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{N} is the vector of nuclide concentrations, and $\mathbf{M}(\phi)$ is the evolution matrix, which depends on the local neutron flux ϕ . This matrix captures all pathways through which nuclides are created or destroyed via fission, absorption, or decay, and is defined as:

$$\mathbf{M}(\phi) = \int \left(\gamma \sigma_f - \sigma_a \right) \phi(E) dE + \mathbf{D} \quad (2)$$

Here, γ is the fission yield matrix, σ_f is the matrix of microscopic fission cross sections, σ_a represents the microscopic absorption cross sections, and \mathbf{D} is the decay matrix. The neutron flux $\phi(E)$ is generally position- and energy-dependent, and is integrated over energy to yield reaction rates.

Under the assumption of constant neutron flux over the time interval $[t, t + dt]$, the solution to this linear system of Ordinary Differential Equations can, in theory, be written analytically using matrix exponentiation, $\mathbf{N}(t + dt) = \exp(\mathbf{M}dt)\mathbf{N}(t) = \mathbf{P} \exp(\mathbf{B}dt)\mathbf{P}^{-1}\mathbf{N}(t)$, where \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{B} are respectively the eigenvector and eigenvalue diagonal matrices, resulting from the diagonalization of $\mathbf{M}(\phi)$. However, for the large and stiff matrices typical of decay problems, this approach can become unstable, causing rounding errors and even unphysical negative nuclide concentrations.

To overcome this, decayFoam implements the already well-established Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM) [9, 10] to evaluate the exponential matrix $\exp(\mathbf{M}dt)$ efficiently and with high numerical stability. CRAM avoids explicit diagonalization and instead approximates the exponential operator using a rational function, making it particularly well-suited for large, sparse, and stiff systems. The Incomplete Partial Fraction (IPF) decomposition of order $k = 16$ is used, which exhibits a lower numerical rounding error compared to Partial Fraction Decomposition (PFD) [11]:

Figure 1. Fuel zones in the Transmutex core (green: inner zone, orange: middle zone, blue: outer zone).

$$\exp(\mathbf{M}dt)\mathbf{N}(t) \approx \hat{r}_{k,k}(\mathbf{M}dt)\mathbf{N}(t) = \alpha_0 \left[\prod_{i=1}^{k/2} \left(1 + 2\text{Re} \left(\alpha_i (\mathbf{M}dt - \theta_i \mathbf{I})^{-1} \right) \right) \right] \mathbf{N}(t) \quad (3)$$

2.2. Implementation in OpenFOAM and coupling in GeN-Foam

The decayFoam solver implements the CRAM algorithm, which provides high accuracy and stability for solving the stiff Bateman equations. The Bateman equations are solved independently in each computational cell, enabling efficient domain decomposition and straightforward parallelization using OpenFOAM's native mesh partitioning tools. This cell-wise formulation is particularly well-suited for high-resolution, distributed simulations where computational cost is a key concern.

To account for neutron flux feedback, decayFoam employs a semi-implicit flux averaging scheme, as described in Ref. [12].

$$\overline{\phi}_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \phi_i = \frac{1}{n} \phi_n + \frac{n-1}{n} \overline{\phi}_{n-1} \quad (4)$$

At each implicit iteration n , the neutron flux field is averaged into $\overline{\phi}_n$ to compute updated reaction rates, providing improved numerical stability while avoiding the need for fully coupled time integration. This approach allows integration with external neutronics solvers while maintaining consistency between evolving material compositions and neutron reaction environments.

Microscopic cross sections (XS) are generated using OpenMC and the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library, as decayFoam has no raw nuclear data processing capabilities. Therefore, decayFoam always relies on external tools to obtain these XS, which are geometry- and material-composition-dependent, similar to the neutronics sub-solver of foamForNuclear, which also relies on external tools to generate MGXS. The native OpenMC function called `openmc.deplete.get_microxs_and_flux` is used to extract all microscopic XS per nuclide and per reaction for a given geometry and composition defined in the OpenMC model. This method implicitly evaluates all averaged reactions XS, including those for nuclides that may not be initially present in the material.

A key limitation of this methodology is that all evaluated microscopic XS are spectrum-dependent.

Figure 2. Evolution of transuranic elements in the inner fuel zone (left) and the power in the three core zones (right) computed with decayFoam (plain lines) and Serpent (dots). Power curves have been scaled for clarity. The relative error is computed as $100 \times \frac{|\text{Serpent} - \text{decayFoam}|}{\text{Serpent}}$.

Since they are averaged using a specific flux spectrum, any significant change in composition or deviation in the neutron energy distribution over time or space renders the XS set no longer valid. Therefore, the solver is not able to perform accurate burnup calculations.

3. CODE-TO-CODE VERIFICATION: DECAY COMPARISON

A simplified reactor case is used to verify the accuracy of the decay calculation capabilities in decayFoam. The reactor studied is the Transmutex core composed of 240 fuel assemblies and three fuel zones. Each fuel assembly is represented by a single cell (see Figure 1). The initial composition at the End-of-Life (EoL) was calculated using the Serpent Monte Carlo code [13], which is widely considered a benchmark tool for depletion and decay studies, assuming a common material composition in each fuel zone. During the cooldown calculation, we assume no external neutron source only to verify the decay process calculation.

The cooldown results obtained with decayFoam are compared against a reference calculation performed using Serpent with the same composition. The comparison focuses on two primary outputs: the time-dependent nuclide composition of specific transuranic elements with noticeable concentration and the total decay power per fuel assembly. These metrics serve as indicators of both numerical accuracy and correct implementation of decay chains and energy-release models.

Figure 3. Coupling scheme for Xenon oscillations in a PWR fuel assembly.

Figure 4. ^{135}Xe axial distribution over time during a Xenon oscillation in a simplified PWR assembly.

Figure 2 shows that decayFoam successfully reproduces the transient features of decay power. This behavior is consistent with the Serpent results, with a maximum deviation in the decay power remaining below 0.4%. The differences in nuclide concentrations are consistently below 0.03% for the nuclide considered, demonstrating a strong agreement between the two codes.

4. APPLICATION

In this section, we present one example of a use case of the decayFoam solver, which is Xenon axial oscillations in a PWR assembly. This example demonstrates the integration of decayFoam into the GeN-Foam application, coupled with the foamForNuclear diffusion-based neutronics sub-solver and thermal-hydraulics sub-solver, to model the dynamic behavior of a simplified PWR fuel assembly. The simulation consists of a 1D axial geometry with 32 cells, representative of a 4m-long PWR fuel assembly, allowing for fast prototyping and efficient coupling of thermal-hydraulics, neutronics, and decay physics.

The coupling architecture used in this demonstration is illustrated in Figure 3. The fuel temperature distribution is mapped from the thermal-hydraulics sub-solver to the neutronics sub-solver, and the nuclide concentration distributions are computed using decayFoam as a sub-solver. On the other hand, the neutronics sub-solver provides neutron flux and power density distribution, respectively, to the decay and thermal-hydraulics sub-solvers.

Figure 5. Fuel temperature axial distribution over time during a Xenon oscillation in a simplified PWR assembly.

MGXSs were computed using OpenMC [5] and the ENDF/B-VII.1 nuclear data library with a standard PWR Beginning-of-Life (BoL) composition. MGXSs were parametrized simultaneously as functions of fuel temperature, ^{135}Xe concentration, and ^{235}U concentration without depletion. This enables the modeling of Doppler feedback and Xenon poisoning, which are key feedback mechanisms. No burnup calculation was performed, and the change in ^{235}U concentration is purely ad hoc and does not correspond to a physical depletion process. Two axial locations, at 1.0 m and 3.4 m, were probed in the GeN-Foam mesh to record the ^{135}Xe concentration and fuel average temperature.

The multi-physics simulation preparation proceeds in two stages: first, the ^{235}U concentration is set to a non-uniform distribution representative of an axially depleted assembly. This simulates several years of typical reactor operation, resulting in a flattened axial neutron flux distribution, which enhances the susceptibility to Xenon-induced oscillations. Second, the axial symmetry of the flux is deliberately perturbed by artificially removing the top quarter of ^{135}Xe to trigger a Xenon oscillation. The transient is recorded 20 hours after the perturbation to allow the solution to stabilize.

This setup is intentionally simplified and does not include validated reactor core data. Due to the lack of access to proprietary plant measurements, some modeling assumptions, such as MGXS parameterization and boundary conditions, are approximate. The goal of this test is not to replicate a specific reactor scenario, but to demonstrate the feasibility of the coupled simulation approach.

Figures 4 and 5 present the evolution of the axial distribution of ^{135}Xe and fuel temperature over time. It can be seen in Figure 4 that the Xenon is effectively going into axial oscillations. The evaluated oscillation period is found to be around 30 hours, which is of the same order of magnitude as in the literature [14]. The Doppler feedback driven by fuel temperature changes plays a stabilizing role in the system. When temperature feedback is included, Xenon oscillations are gradually dampened, and the core approaches equilibrium after approximately 200 hours. In contrast, when Doppler feedback is disabled, the oscillations persist significantly longer, reflecting the loss of a stabilizing mechanism. The

temperature fluctuations are also pronounced; at $Z=3.4$ m, the peak temperature difference reaches over 100 K, underscoring the potential thermal impact of Xenon dynamics on fuel performance.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1. Hypothesis, simplifications, and limitations

The decayFoam solver has been designed to support control and safety-oriented studies. It aims to provide a fast and flexible tool capable of capturing key physical trends for multi-physics scenarios involving neutron poison buildup and/or decay heat from fission products, while it does not have the required functionalities to perform depletion calculations.

A central feature of the framework is its ability to support in-memory coupling between decay, neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and thermo-mechanics through the foamForNuclear project with the GeN-Foam application. This allows for consistent and tightly integrated simulations where feedback mechanisms, such as temperature effects on reactivity and nuclide poison concentration affecting local power, can be modeled in a time-resolved, spatially distributed manner. Such coupling is essential for capturing transient behaviors and feedback loops that are otherwise difficult to represent in decoupled workflows.

By combining accurate decay with solver interoperability, decayFoam opens the door to non-standard safety scenarios that fall outside the scope of traditional analyses. These may include the investigation of localized feedback instabilities or long-term degradation phenomena under shutdown conditions. However, the results should be interpreted within the limitations of the modeling fidelity and cross-section data used, and viewed as complementary to, not a substitute for, detailed Monte Carlo or experimentally validated approaches.

Here is a summary of the limitations and simplifications of the current decayFoam solver:

- Only the nuclides that appear in the decay chain provided as user input are transported. This allows the solver to reduce the nuclide vector and the computational time/memory.
- All the decay energy emitted is absorbed in the same cell for decay power density evaluation. This may be true for alpha and beta decay, but it is arguably questionable for neutron and gamma decay. This could be improved by adding a discrete ordinate solver to transport the neutral particles.
- Only (n, fission), (n, alpha), (n, p) reactions are counted in the energy absorbed in the cell for neutron-induced power density evaluation.
- The neutron flux is assumed to be constant during a solver iteration.
- The averaged microscopic cross-sections evaluated for decayFoam are time-independent. The averaged XS should change according to the neutron flux spectrum affected by the geometry, material composition, temperature, and self-shielding.

5.2. Conclusion and Perspectives

The decayFoam solver presents a promising solution for advanced multi-physics reactor simulations involving decay power and neutronics poisoning. Its modular design and compatibility with foamForNuclear sub-solvers make it well-suited for applications that require tightly coupled decay, thermal-hydraulics, neutronics, and thermo-mechanics. In particular, its in-memory data exchange structure enables efficient multi-physics reactor analysis using the GeN-Foam application.

The capabilities of decayFoam extend beyond conventional reactor analysis, where it can be used to quantify helium production in fuel pellets, an important factor in fuel swelling, mechanical interaction between the pellets and the materials. Similarly, the solver can be used to track activated nuclides in liquid-metal systems, which makes it valuable for modeling contamination in lead-cooled reactors.

Beyond reactor design, its flexibility could also support long-term radionuclide transport studies in deep geological repositories or atmospheric dispersion assessments following accident scenarios.

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